

Sociodemographics

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

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- 1) Birth date _____

 - 2) What is the work or activity of your father? _____

 - 3) What is the work or activity of your mother? _____

 - 4) During the week at school, you are...
 - External
 - Half border
 - Internal

 - 5) Is there a garden, a vegetable garden or a field in the family (or correspondent) in which you live?
 - Oui
 - Non